

The *Revista Costarricense de Orientación* (RCO) invites authors to submit articles for its
2027 special issue:

Innovation, Technologies, and Digital Tools for Guidance

Articles must be submitted by January 31st, 2027.

Texts in Spanish, English, and Portuguese will be accepted.

All articles must be submitted via the following link:

<https://www.rco.cpocr.org/index.php/rco/index>

Introduction

The expansion of digital technologies has profoundly altered the conditions under which contemporary life is organized. This influence often goes unnoticed, as the way digital technology shapes daily life is not always consciously recognized. Therefore, the integration of digital technologies into guidance counseling cannot be reduced to a technical adaptation of their role; rather, it requires a careful examination of the social, cultural, and ethical transformations that underpin these changes. Thus, the central question is no longer whether or not technologies should be introduced into guidance processes, but rather: who are the individuals receiving guidance today, and what is the purpose of this guidance in the digital age? How does guidance practice respond to the characteristics of people and to contemporary contexts? And what challenges are emerging for guidance counseling?

Given these tensions, the digital age is not only reshaping people's identities and careers, but also the conditions under which guidance professionals fulfill their purpose: to foster the holistic development of human beings throughout their lives. Therefore, this special issue, far from offering definitive answers, aims to create a space for critical reflection, questioning, and rethinking guidance practice in a world where digital technology influences subjectivity, attention, desire, and ways of understanding one's own existence.

Authors are invited to critically analyze the relationship between career guidance, innovation, and digital technologies, moving beyond an instrumental view focused solely on the use of specific tools, applications, or platforms. The scope of interest extends beyond simply describing technological experiences; it seeks to explore how digital conditions mediate, transform, or create tensions within career guidance processes, particularly those related to self-knowledge, identity formation, sense of purpose, decision-making, and career development across diverse populations and contexts.

Works are expected to develop a critical exercise aimed at analyzing existing discourses, theories, and practices, with the goal of generating alternative readings, formulating new questions, and proposing transformative perspectives on the field of guidance in digitally mediated contexts.

The journal accepts scientific articles (research, literature reviews, or systematization of experiences) and essays. If you have questions regarding the special issue, please contact us at the following email address: revista@cpocr.com

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